

Do immune cytokines (TNF- α) have a role in neuropathic pain?

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ABSTRACT The immune system consists of specialized cells known as immune cells that release mediators termed as cytokines. The immune system is activated in response to tissue injury or disease and initiates the process of inflammation that results in the development of inflammatory pain. Similarly, injury secondary to disease or lesion to the somatosensory system can activate an immune system that causes functional and structural changes in the somatosensory system that results in the development of neuropathic pain. The International Association for Study of Pain (IASP) therefore defines neuropathic pain as “pain caused by a lesion or disease of the somatosensory system”. Emerging evidence suggests that immune cytokines play a pivotal role in the pathogenesis of neuropathic pain in animal models of NP. Human trials confirming such findings are increasing in number. However, failure of therapeutic trials targeting specific cytokines raised controversy. Animal research confirms the role of immune cytokines in the pathogenesis of neuropathic pain.

KEYWORDS cytokines, TNF, neuropathic pain

Introduction

The immune system consists of specialized cells known as immune cells that release mediators termed as cytokines. The immune system is activated in response to tissue injury or disease and initiates the process of inflammation that results in the development of inflammatory pain [1]. Similarly, injury secondary to disease or lesion to the somatosensory system can activate an immune system that causes functional and structural changes in the somatosensory system that results in the development of neuropathic pain [2]. The International Association for Study of Pain (IASP) therefore defines neuropathic pain as “pain caused by a lesion or disease of the somatosensory system” [3]. Emerging evidence suggests that immune cytokines play a pivotal role in the pathogenesis of neuropathic pain in animal models of NP [4]. Human trials confirming such findings are increasing in number. However, failure of therapeutic trials targeting specific

cytokines raised controversy [5]. Animal research confirms the role of immune cytokines in the pathogenesis of neuropathic pain [4, 6-13].

Discussion:

Immune cytokines are low molecular weight glycoproteins that are secreted by immune cells such as macrophages, T lymphocytes, and neutrophils [14]. Immune cells and their cytokines initiate a cascade of neuropathological events that start at the site of nerve injury and progress to involve dorsal root ganglion, the spinal cord dorsal horn and possibly supraspinal structures in the CNS [12]. Cytokines are also secreted by non-immune cells such as keratinocytes and dendritic cells of the skin, and Schwann cells and glial cells of the nervous system [15]. Cytokines are produced in response to disease or tissue injury and act as mediators regulating the function and differentiation of neighbouring cells [14]. There are five main categories of cytokines: interleukins, interferons, tumour necrosis factors, growth factors and chemokines (chemotactic cytokines) [16]. Cytokines are also classified as pro-inflammatory and anti-inflammatory cytokines that regulate the process of inflammation [16]. The main pro-inflammatory cytokines are tumour necrosis factor alpha (TNF- α), interleukin-1 β (IL-1 β), IL-6; whereas the most studied anti-inflammatory mediator is IL-10 [17]. It is also well known that TNF- α , IL-1 and IL-6 induce

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the production of each other, acting synergistically to sustain the inflammatory response whereas anti-inflammatory cytokines (IL-10, IL-4, TGF- β) act as endogenous feedback inhibitors to maintain a balanced immune response [17]. The local activation of pro-inflammatory cytokines that is necessary to initiate the healing processes of the injured nerve must be paralleled by an adequate trigger of anti-inflammatory cytokines that would act as suppressors [18]. Evidence suggests that pro-inflammatory cytokines play an essential role in the pathogenesis of neuropathic pain [17]. However, it has recently emerged that neuropathic pain pathogenesis and maintenance are not confined only to the changes in the activity of neuronal systems, but involve interactions between neurons, inflammatory immune cells, glia and microglia cells, as well as a wide cascade of pro and anti-inflammatory cytokines [11, 13].

Interactions of the immune system and the somatosensory system is bidirectional and occur at all levels including skin, peripheral nerves, dorsal root ganglion, dorsal and ventral horns of the spinal cord, and supraspinal sites such as the thalamus, hypothalamus, rostral ventral medulla (RVM), and periaqueductal grey (PAG) [13]. Cytokines are the essential means of this interaction [19]. The role of cytokines in neuro-immune interaction is well defined at the skin, peripheral nerve, dorsal root ganglion and dorsal horn of spinal cord levels, however, their action at a supraspinal level still not much clear [13].

Immune Cytokines modulates neuroimmune interaction in peripheral nerve injury:

Peripheral nerve injury could be sequelae of trauma, infection, toxin, metabolite or immune-based diseases [13]. Injured nerves undergo processes of degeneration (e.g. Wallerian degeneration following axon transection) and regeneration with the interaction of the immune system [20]. Neuroimmune interaction is initiated with the release of cytokines (IL-6, IL-1 β , TNF- α) from resident immune cells (macrophages and mast cells) and non-immune cells (Schwann cells and Langerhans cells) [9,11]. Chemokines (CCL2) attract circulating macrophages and T-lymphocytes to the site of injury through the leaky blood-nerve barrier [12]. Nociceptors are highly sensitive to immune cytokines, which activate and sensitize the neuron.

Interleukin-1 β , IL-6, and TNF- α sensitize temperature chemical sensitive TRPV and TRPA family channels that produce thermal hyperalgesia [19]. A load of inflammatory mediators at the site of nerve injury can provoke spontaneous electrophysiological activity in nociceptive fibres, causing an amplification of abnormal signals that reach DRG sensory neurons and satellite cells. Similarly, at dorsal root ganglion (DRG), cytokines activation causes structural and functional changes such as satellite cells proliferation, macrophage and T-lymphocytes infiltration, and increased expression of cytokines receptors, e.g. TNFR and CCR2 resulting in increased DRG neuronal excitability [13]. Sacerdote et al., by using chronic constriction injury (CCI) model in animals demonstrated that TNF- α and IL-1 β are responsible for developing neuropathic pain while IL-6 and IL-1 β maintain neuropathic pain as allodynia and mechanical hyperalgesia (Sacerdote et al., 2013). TNF- α appeared six hours after the injury and disappeared after three days that explain negative results of trials of etanercept (a TNF- α blocker) [5]

Immune cytokines act at the central nervous system:

Neuroimmune interactions also occur at CNS in response to peripheral nerve injury or direct injury or disease of the CNS

and accelerate the process of central sensitisation leading to neuropathic pain. Microglia, resident macrophages in the central nervous, are activated by cytokines and chemokines (CCL2) that are secreted in response to injury or disease of the somatosensory system. Activated microglia proliferate and further release pro-inflammatory cytokines, undergo morphological and functional changes such as expression of surface proteins and gene expression. This process termed as microgliosis that occur at dorsal horn of spinal cord, thalamus, hypothalamus, RVM, and PAG [21]. A PET scan study on amputees with chronic phantom limb pain suggests that microgliosis occurs in the thalamus [22] Cytokines (TNF- α and IL-1 β) released by microglia disrupts the balance of central pain excitatory and inhibitory system by increasing excitatory synaptic transmission and reducing inhibitory transmission an essential step in central sensitization of pain [23]. However, the neuroimmune response of CNS secondary to peripheral nerve injury is not well understood as studies showing conflicting results [13]. Direct injury to CNS cause central neuropathic pain [24]. Immune cytokines also play a role in the underlying mechanism of central neuropathic pain. For instance, high levels of cytokines and chemokines detected in the CSF of patients with spinal cord injury [25].

Evidence of the role of cytokines in disease affecting somatosensory system producing neuropathic pain:

Neuropathic pain is a common sequela of conditions that cause nerve degeneration such as Guillain-Barre Syndrome (GBS), Multiple Sclerosis, and CRPS. Degenerating neurons activate resident immune cells (macrophages and mast cells) that release cytokines (IL-6, IL-1 β , TNF- α , chemokines) causing the recruitment of circulating immune cells through the leaky blood-nerve barrier. A cascade of events occurs such as increased level of pro-inflammatory cytokines, expression of cytokine receptors and membrane hyperexcitability. Patients with CRPS have increased the cutaneous concentration of TNF- α , interleukins, and chemokines [26, 27]. Also, patients with small fibre neuropathy have significantly high levels of pro-inflammatory cytokines in the skin compared with healthy controls [28], and Immune-mediated neuropathy in GBS generate neuropathic pain [29]. Multiple Sclerosis (MS) is an inflammatory disease of the CNS, one-third of MS patients have neuropathic pain and role of microglia, macrophages, T-lymphocytes is attributed to the episodes of neuropathic pain [30]. IL-10 prevented the onset of allodynia and inhibited glial activation in an animal MS model [31] whereas interferon β -1a improved pain scores of patients with MS [32]. Such findings confirm the role of immune cytokines in the pathogenesis of neuropathic pain in diseases affecting the somatosensory system.

Clinical studies targeting immune cells, glial cells and immune cytokines show conflicting results:

Randomised controlled trials using systemic or subcutaneous anti-TNF- α therapy failed to prove its efficacy [33]. Only small-scale studies or case series show some positive results [13] although Propentofylline that prevent microglial activation found to be effective in rodents but not effective in human trails [13]. There are numerous positive and negative trials discussed in recent reviews on the role of the immune system in the pathogenesis of neuropathic pain in animals and humans [4, 12, 13, 34]. The problem of the failure of human trials is not limited to the field of pain only [35,36]. Improvement in the translational research design [37] more emphasis on research finding the role of

anti-inflammatory cytokines [6] would likely to achieve success in discovering effective and safe analgesic agents.

Conclusion

Immune cytokines play a vital role in the pathogenesis of neuropathic pain. Evidence supporting their role in peripheral neuropathic pain is convincing. However, the supraspinal mechanism is still not clear. Very few clinical trials prove the efficacy of therapy targeting specific immune cytokines that indicate the need for therapy targeting to shift the balance from pro-inflammatory to anti-inflammatory response.

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